

Influence of H⁺ ions and γ -ray irradiation on multiferroic Bi_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}MnO₃ thin films

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Abstract

Polycrystalline Multiferroic materials having coupled electric, magnetic and elastic orderings provide a platform for memory and logic devices. Controlling polarization switching mechanisms in ferroelectric and multiferroic materials is a critical step towards the oxide-based electronic devices including data storage devices, tunneling barriers and field-effect transistors. Bismuth manganite (BiMnO₃) has been regarded as one of the prominent multiferroic materials. Here Bi_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}MnO₃ (BCMO) thin films were deposited on Si (100) substrate using RF magnetron sputtering. The grown films have been subjected H⁺ ions and γ - ray irradiation to enhance its magneto electric coupling for memory devices. Moreover, the structural, elemental, magnetic and electrical properties of these irradiated BCMO films have been analyzed.

Keywords: Bi_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}MnO₃ thin films, sputtering, ferroelectricity, ferromagnetism

Figure: XPS survey spectra of (a) H⁺ ions irradiated (b) γ -ray irradiated Bi_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}MnO₃ film

References

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